

MATHEMATICAL PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS: BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GAME-BASED ACTIVITY SHEETS

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ABSTRACT

This research employed a descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement among Grade 7 learners at Libo-o Integrated School during the school year 2023-2024. The study involved 24 purposively sampled respondents, with data collected using a researcher-developed multiple-choice (30-item) test. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and means were utilized, while the inferential statistical tools employed included the Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis test, and Spearman's rho. The findings revealed that the level of mathematical problem-solving skills was at an average level, while overall mathematics achievement was considered satisfactory. The study also examined the influence of gender and socioeconomic status on mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement. It was determined that socioeconomic status does not significantly impact mathematical problem-solving skills or mathematics achievement. However, in terms of gender, females tend to have higher averages in both mathematical problem-solving skills and overall mathematics achievement. Furthermore, the study uncovered a significant positive correlation between mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement, emphasizing the interdependence of these two variables. To address the research objectives, the study proposed the development of "Mathemagical: Game-Based Activity Sheets for Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills," which aims to enhance mathematical problem-solving skills by utilizing gamified learning experiences that engage learners in meaningful and enjoyable activities. In conclusion, this study offers valuable insights into the

dynamics of mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement among Grade 7 learners.

Keywords: *Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills, Game-Based Activity*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematical problem-solving is a crucial aspect of mathematics teaching and learning, influencing global curricula and attracting interest from mathematics education researchers for its long-standing importance (Liljedahl, Santos-Trigo, Malaspina, and Bruder, 2016). Numerous studies in educational evaluation have shown that pupils have difficulty completing mathematical problem-solving tasks. These difficulties are mostly brought on by difficulties in solving problems. Students adopt techniques that can be categorized as either problem-focused or emotion-focused coping methods to deal with these difficulties (Vidad and Quimbo, 2021). To foster critical thinking and problem-solving skills, students must first acquire a strong foundation in essential competencies. In order to promote meaningful learning in a math classroom, it is essential to have learning materials that align with the students' specific context readily accessible (Suguitan and Natividad, 2022).

In the research conducted by Layug, Valerio, and Capones (2021), it was reported that in 2018, the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) ranked the Philippines as the second lowest out of 79 participating nations worldwide. This suggests that the mathematics skills of students in the Philippines are quite weak. In the published work of Balagtas (2020), the Philippines likewise did poorly in Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), which is consistent with the PISA 2018 results. Likewise, over the course of its involvement in the investigation, Filipino kids performed far worse on the TIMSS mathematics achievement test than Singapore, Taiwan, and Korea, which are some neighboring countries. Based on TIMSS (2019), the Philippines did not fare better in the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study.

By providing relevant learning activities, the goal was to motivate students to continually improve their math knowledge and skills, ultimately dispelling the misconception that mathematics is a challenging subject. The purpose of this study was to assess and develop appropriate game-based activity sheets for the improvement of mathematical problem-solving skills in Grade 7 learners.

Research Questions

The main objective of this study is to determine the Math achievement of the respondents in mathematical problem-solving skills as a basis for the development of game-based activity sheets.

Specifically, this study seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents when taken as a whole and when classified according to sex and socio-economic status?
2. What is the level of mathematics achievement among the respondents as a whole and when grouped as to sex and socio-economic status?
3. What is the level of mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents as a whole and when grouped as to sex and socio-economic status?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents when classified as to sex and socio-economic status?
5. Is there a significant difference in the level of mathematics achievement among the respondents when classified as sex and socio-economic status?
6. Is there a significant relationship between Math achievement and mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents when classified as sex and socio-economic status?
7. What intervention can be developed based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed descriptive-correlational research. Descriptive-correlational research is a type of research that is used to determine the relationship between two variables.

The respondents of the study were twenty-four (24) Grade seven learners of Libo-o Integrated School. The researchers utilized purposive sampling in choosing the said respondents for the study. This sampling method was chosen due to the limited number of respondents who fit the profile required for the study. According to Foley (2018), purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their study. The tools that were utilized by the researchers in gathering the data were the researcher-made and expert-validated multiple-choice test. The researchers initially created a 30-item multiple-choice test. The instrument underwent expert consultation and validation before being implemented in face-to-face testing with a purposively selected learner. The reliability score was 0.75 Cronbach's alpha.

Upon receiving permission from the Dean of the School of Teachers Education to conduct research outside the school, the researchers sent a letter to the School Division of Passi City. After the letters were signed, the researchers sent a letter to the school principal of Agdayao Integrated School for pilot testing of the research instrument. The data was then sent to the statistician for a reliability test. After the statistician confirmed that the research instrument was reliable for the study, the researcher sent a letter to the school principal of Libo-o Integrated School for the conduct of the study. A face-to-face implementation was observed. Once the data was gathered from all the respondents, the researchers compiled and analyzed the data. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to quantify the data and determine the association of variables included in the study. The data was analyzed using Frequency Count and Percentage, Mean, Mann-Whitney U test, Kruskal-Wallis H Test, and Spearman's rho. Frequency count and percentage were used

to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of sex and socio-economic status. Mean was used to find out the mathematical problem-solving skills of the respondents. The Mann-Whitney U Test was used to determine if there was a significant difference in the level of mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents when classified according to sex. The Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the level of mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents when classified according to socio-economic status (low-income class, middle-income class, and high-income class). Spearman's rho was used to determine the relationship between Math achievement and mathematical problem-solving skills of the respondents.

RESULTS

Profile of the Respondents. Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents. Out of 24 respondents, 13 or 54.2% are males, and 11 or 45.8% are females. In terms of socio-economic status, 1 or 4.2% are classified as poor, 13 or 54.2% as low income, 7 or 29.2% as lower middle-income, and 3 or 12.5% as upper middle-income. This indicates a larger male participation in the study. According to Herbert, Joyline, and Elliot's (2020) study, there were 93 male learners and 87 female learners as respondents. These findings suggest a higher representation of male participants compared to their female counterparts. Sintema and Jita's (2022) study involved 490 students, 288 boys, and 202 girls from three schools, and it assessed mathematical problem-solving beliefs using a questionnaire. The results indicated a higher representation of male participants in mathematics surveys.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Group	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Sex			
	Male	13	54.2
	Female	11	45.8
	Total	24	100
Socio-Economic Status			
	Poor	1	4.2
	Low Income	13	54.2
	Lower Middle-Income	7	29.2
	Upper Middle-Income	3	12.5
	Total	24	100

Level of Mathematics Achievement as to Sex and Socio-Economic Status. The results show that the level of mathematics achievement, taken as a whole, was satisfactory (M=81.38, SD=5.52). When grouped according to sex, males had a mean score of 78.61 (SD=3.07), while females had a mean score of 84.64 (SD=6.10). In terms of socio-economic status, lower middle-income students had a mean score of 82.71 (SD=7.59), which was interpreted as "satisfactory". This was followed by low-income students (M=77.00, SD=4.66), upper middle-income students (M=78.33, SD=4.16), and poor students (M=77.00). The findings of Peteros, Gamboa, Etcuban, Dinauanao, Sito, and Arcadio (2020) suggest that respondents believe in their ability to perform well in the subject, especially when they put more effort into math-related tasks. The study by Garinganao and Bearneza (2021) found that the average proficiency in algebraic skills among Grade 7 students in a Chinese high school suggests that they have a solid grasp of concepts such as signed numbers, arithmetic, fractions, exponents, and factors. The students' competence in algebraic skills significantly influences their overall academic performance in mathematics.

Table 2
Level of Mathematics Achievement

Group	Categories	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Description
Sex	Male	78.62	13	3.07	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>
	Female	84.64	11	6.10	<i>Satisfactory</i>
	Total	81.38	24	5.52	<i>Satisfactory</i>
Socio-Economic Status	Poor	77.00	1	0	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>
	Low Income	81.69	13	4.66	<i>Satisfactory</i>
	Lower Middle- Income	82.71	7	7.59	<i>Satisfactory</i>
	Upper Middle- Income	78.33	3	4.16	<i>Fairly Satisfactory</i>
	Total	81.38	24	5.52	<i>Satisfactory</i>

Note: Outstanding (90-100), Very Satisfactory (85-89), Satisfactory (80-84), Fairly Satisfactory (75-79), and Did Not Meet Expectation (Below 75).

Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills as to Sex and Socio-Economic Status. The results showed that the level of mathematical problem-solving skills, taken as a whole, was "average" (M=14.29, SD=4.88). When grouped according to sex, males

had a mean of 12.46 (SD=3.31), while females had a mean of 16.45 (SD=5.66). As for socio-economic status, lower-middle-income was "average" (M=15.4, SD=6.39), followed by low income (M=14.77, SD=4.27), upper-middle-income (M=13.00, SD=1.00), and poor (M=6.00, SD=0). Incebacak and Ersoy (2016) found that students generally performed well when solving problems similar to those they had encountered before. They were able to correctly understand and distinguish between the given information and the requirements of the problem. Quinto (2021) revealed that the participants in the study possessed a remarkable comprehension of GBL. Moreover, they held positive attitudes toward GBL and believed that its integration into education could enhance their understanding of mathematics. Problem-solving is an individualized process that requires various strategies to tackle. Prema and Sathiskumar's (2021) findings also demonstrated that demographic variables such as gender have a significant effect on the academic achievement of high school students. Female students possess significantly higher academic achievement than their male counterparts.

Table 3
Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills

Group	Categories	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Description
Sex	Male	12.46	13	3.31	<i>Below Average</i>
	Female	16.45	11	5.66	<i>Average</i>
	Total	14.29	24	4.88	<i>Average</i>
Socio-Economic Status	Poor	6.00	1	0.	<i>Poor</i>
	Low Income	14.77	13	4.27	<i>Average</i>
	Lower Middle- Income	15.14	7	6.39	<i>Average</i>
	Upper Middle- Income	13.00	3	1.00	<i>Average</i>
	Total	14.29	24	4.88	<i>Average</i>

Note: Advanced (25-30), Above Average (19-24), Average (13-18), Below Average (7-12), and Poor (0-6).

Difference in the Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills as to Sex.

Differences in the level of mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents were analyzed based on their sex. Table 4.1 shows that the Mann-Whitney U results revealed a significant difference in the level of mathematical problem-solving skills

according to sex ($z=-2.125$, $p=.034$). As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. Guler and Cekmez's (2023) research indicates that problem-solving abilities among middle school students were similar between genders, with females scoring slightly higher on average (mean = 3.53 compared to 3.33 for boys).

Table 4.1

Difference in the Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills as to Sex

Pair	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	p	Decision
Sex	35.000	126.000	-2.125	.034	Significant

**Significant @ $p<0.05$*

Difference in the Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills as to Socio-Economic Status. The Kruskal-Wallis H test revealed that there is no significant difference in mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents based on socio-economic status ($df=3$, $p=.302$). This indicates that the mathematical problem-solving skills of the respondents do not vary with socio-economic status. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It was found that the mathematical problem-solving abilities of individuals were indirectly influenced by the educational levels of both parents, with family income playing a mediating role (Amalina and Vidakovick, 2023).

Table 4.2

Difference in the Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills as to Socio-Economic Status

Pair	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	p	Decision
Socio-Economic Status	3.651	3	.302	Not Significant

**Significant @ $p<0.05$*

Difference in the level of Mathematics Achievement as to Sex and Socio-Economic Status. In Table 5.1, the Mann-Whitney U results revealed that there is a significant difference in the level of mathematics achievement among the respondents according to sex ($z=-2.648$, $p=.008$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The findings from the study conducted by De Jesus (2023) suggest that students perceive MathScore as a valuable supplemental tool in their mathematics learning journey. The research revealed a significant difference in students' mathematics achievement based on their sex and total engagement time in MathScore per week. According to Egorova and Chertkova (2016), it was observed that sex differences existed across various measures of mathematical achievement. Specifically, girls demonstrated higher math grades in school compared to boys, whereas boys surpassed girls in their scores on the Unified State Exam (USE) in

mathematics. The variability among boys was greater, with a higher proportion of boys excelling at the upper end of the performance distribution. Notably, girls who held a positive perception of their math abilities outperformed boys on math tests.

Table 5.1

Difference in the level of Mathematics Achievement as to Sex

Pair	Mann-Whitney U	Wilcoxon W	Z	p	Decision
Sex	26.000	117.000	-2.648	.008	Significant

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Difference in the level of Mathematics Achievement as Socio-Economic Status.

The Kruskal Wallis H test revealed that there is no significant difference in mathematics achievement among the respondents based on socio-economic status ($df=3$, $p=.515$). This indicates that the mathematics achievement of the respondents does not vary according to socio-economic status. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Cabuquin and Abocejo (2023) found that their study did not identify any significant differences between male and female students, suggesting that both genders have equal potential for academic success. The study concludes that fostering mathematical proficiency is crucial for academic achievement, and secondary education institutions should ensure that students, regardless of gender, have ample opportunities to engage with mathematics through classes and various activities. Academic achievement is significantly influenced by socioeconomic status, with students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds generally performing better than their counterparts from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, who face a variety of obstacles to their academic advancement (Aashiq, Zeb, Yan, and Tahir, 2023).

Table 5.2

Difference in the level of Mathematics Achievement as to Socio-Economic Status

Pair	Kruskal-Wallis H	df	p	Decision
Socio-Economic Status	2.288	3	.515	Not Significant

*Significant @ $p < 0.05$

Spearman's rho Result on the Relationship between the Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills and Mathematics Achievement.

Table 6 shows the relationship between the level of mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement, which is highly positively correlated with $r = 0.725$. The results also showed

that there is a significant relationship between mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement ($p = 0.000$, $p < 0.001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. The study conducted by Hassan and Rahman (2017) highlights the significant role of problem-solving skills and metacognitive awareness in enhancing secondary school students' mathematics achievement. It is crucial to help students develop both metacognitive awareness and problem-solving skills, as both are related to mathematics achievement. According to Maheswari and Benjamin (2015), students with a limited understanding of mathematical concepts exhibit poor problem-solving skills. Those with moderate proficiency in mathematical concepts demonstrate average problem-solving abilities, while students with advanced mathematical skills showcase high problem-solving skills. Furthermore, there is a high positive correlation between problem-solving skills and academic achievement in mathematics among 7th-standard pupils.

Table 6

Relationship between the Level of Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills and Mathematics Achievement

	Problem- Solving Skills		
	r value	p-value	Description
Math Achievement	.725	.000	Significant

** $p < 0.0001$, Highly Significant*

Mathemagical: Game-Based Activity Sheets for Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills. The figure below shows the output of the study, "Mathemagical: Game-Based Activity Sheets for Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills." The content of this output consists of the first quarter competencies of Grade 7. Utilizing games as a pedagogical tool in the teaching of mathematics has been recognized as an effective approach to making mathematical learning enjoyable (Beyhan and Tural, 2007; as cited by Baskahya, 2021). This strategy not only fosters a positive learning experience but also helps counteract any misconceptions students may have about mathematics. Numerous mathematician-designed games have emerged, contributing to the advancement of mathematical skills and instilling a sense of enjoyment in the subject Baskahya, 2021). According to the findings of Rondina and Roble (2019), using mathematical game-based design activities, such as "A Line to Win," proved to be an effective method for enhancing students' computational skills.

Figure 4. Shows the cover output of the study.

The fifteen competencies in the first quarter of Mathematics 7 were divided into three different games; each set of games has five competencies. The goal of these game-based activity sheets is to develop the mathematical problem-solving skills of seventh-grade learners. Additionally, to make the learning process effective and enjoyable at the same time, and to create a meaningful learning experience through the games that are presented in this output, the researchers created three different kinds of game-based

activity sheets, namely “Math-tastic Bingo, Math Race, and Math and Friends Scavenger Hunt.”

Math-tastic Bingo. The Math-tastic Bingo includes five competencies from the first quarter: illustrating well-defined sets, subsets, universal sets, null sets, the cardinality of sets, union, and intersection of sets, and different of two sets; solving problems involving sets with the use of a Venn diagram; representing the absolute value of a number line as the distance of a number from 0; performing fundamental operations on integers; and illustrating the different properties of operations on integers. The primary objective of the game is for players to achieve bingo by marking off numbers that correspond to the answers of provided questions or situations. The game offers three distinct playing options. Firstly, players can opt for a "free-tastic" table or blank space, allowing them to decide how to arrange numbers 1-24 on their bingo card. Secondly, the "speed round" introduces a time limit, challenging players to answer questions within the allotted time. The winner is determined by the player with the most marked squares. Lastly, the "math facts mix-up" involves presenting mathematical problems on separate cards, shuffling them, and calling them out randomly, introducing an element of surprise and additional challenges for the players.

Math Race. The Math Race includes five competencies: describing principal roots and determining whether they are rational or irrational; determining between what two integers the square root of a number is; estimating the square root of a whole number to the nearest hundredth; expressing rational numbers from fraction form to decimal form and vice versa; and performing operations on rational numbers. The aim of this game is for players to reach the finish line. They need to start by solving the equation that is posted on every road or way; getting the correct answer will advance them to the finish line. The first player to reach the finish line will be the winner.

Math and Friends Scavenger Hunt. The Math, Friends, and Scavenger Hunt includes five competencies: plotting irrational numbers (up to the square root) on a number line; illustrating the different subsets of real numbers; arranging real numbers in increasing or decreasing order and on a number line; writing numbers in scientific notation and vice versa; and represent real-life situations and solve problems involving real numbers. This game is fun and exciting and promotes teamwork and collaboration. The goal of this game is to explore by finding the answers in a designated area. The team should use creativity and teamwork to calculate solutions to uncover hidden answers. Each group will have a time limit and another minute to review answers and solutions. The team with the highest score will be the winner.

The game-based approach to learning involves students working in groups to engage with educational materials interactively and enjoyably, mastering fundamental competencies. Employing the game method in education aids students in comprehending the subject matter (Hastuti, Mustikaningtyas, & Widiyatmoko, 2014; as cited from Raupu,

Utari, Nursyamsi, and Marwiyah, 2022). In the Philippines, the Department of Education created Learning Activity Sheets for all grade levels for the 2020-2021 school year. These sheets include activities like coloring, word search, mazes, and math tests. They should also use manipulative, authentic materials and accommodate cultural, linguistic, and racial diversity. Games can serve as a useful starting point for daily study (Suguitan and Natividad, 2022).

DISCUSSION

The study involved purposively selected grade seven learners from Libo-o Integrated School, with both genders adequately represented. More males participated in the study than females. As for socio-economic status, more respondents were from low-income classes.

The overall level of mathematics achievement was deemed "satisfactory." When grouped according to sex, males performed at a "fairly satisfactory" level, while females achieved a "satisfactory" level. In terms of socio-economic status, those with low income and lower-middle income demonstrated a "satisfactory" performance, whereas individuals with poor and upper-middle income achieved a "fairly satisfactory" level.

The overall level of mathematical problem-solving skills was assessed as "average." When grouped according to sex, males were "below average," while females were deemed "average." In terms of socio-economic status, individuals with low income, lower-middle income, and upper-middle income were all evaluated as having "average" mathematical problem-solving skills.

There is a significant difference in the level of mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents when grouped according to sex. There is no significant difference in the mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents when grouped according to socio-economic status.

There is a significant difference in the level of mathematics achievement among the respondents according to sex. While there is no significant difference in mathematics achievement among the respondents according to socio-economic status.

There is a significant relationship between the level of mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement, which is highly positively correlated.

The overall proficiency in mathematical problem-solving skills was assessed as "average." In response to these findings, an intervention titled "Mathemagical: Game-Based Activity Sheets for Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills" was developed.

Conclusions

In light of the findings presented, the following conclusions were drawn:

Based on the respondents' profiles, most of the respondents are male rather than female. Additionally, a notable majority of participants originate from families with lower income levels. Sintema and Jita's (2022) study involved 490 students, 288 boys, and 202 girls, from three schools, assessing mathematical problem-solving beliefs through a questionnaire. The results show a higher representation of male participants in mathematics surveys.

It has been found in the study that the level of mathematics achievement as a whole was satisfactory. When grouped according to sex and socio-economic status, females interpreted the mean as satisfactory, which is higher than the male mean. Learners who were in the lower middle-income class showed a satisfactory level of mathematics achievement. This means that the female learners and lower-middle-income class respondents are satisfactory compared to males and other socio-economic classes. The study of Garinganao and Bearneza (2021) found that the average proficiency in algebraic skills among Grade 7 students in a Chinese high school suggests that they have a solid grasp of concepts such as signed numbers, arithmetic, fractions, exponents, and factors. The students' competence in algebraic skills significantly influences their overall academic performance in mathematics.

The research indicates that overall mathematical problem-solving skills are at an average level. When examining the data based on gender and socio-economic status, females perceived the mean as average, surpassing the male mean. Similarly, learners from the lower middle-income class, low-income class, and upper-middle-income class demonstrated an average proficiency in mathematical problem-solving. In essence, this suggests that female learners and those from the lower middle-income class, low-income class, and upper-middle-income class are on par with their male counterparts and individuals from other socio-economic classes in terms of mathematical problem-solving skills. Incebacak and Ersoy (2016) found that students generally performed well when solving problems similar to those they had encountered before. They were able to correctly understand and distinguish between the given information and the problem's requirements. Furthermore, Prema and Sathiskumar's (2021) findings exhibited that demographic variables such as gender have a significant effect on the academic achievement of high school students. The female students possess significantly higher academic achievement than their male counterparts.

The Mann-Whitney U test indicates that there is no statistically significant distinction in the proficiency of mathematical problem-solving skills based on sex among the participants. Similarly, the results of the Kruskal-Wallis H test suggest that there is no noteworthy variation in mathematical problem-solving skills among the respondents

concerning their socio-economic status. According to Guler and Cekmez's (2023) research, middle school students' problem-solving abilities were comparable between genders, with females scoring slightly higher on average. Additionally, the mathematical problem-solving abilities of individuals were found to be indirectly affected by the educational levels of both parents, with family income playing a mediating role (Amalina and Vidakovick, 2023).

Mann-Whitney U test results revealed that there is a significant difference in the level of mathematics achievement among the respondents according to sex. While Kruskal Wallis H test result revealed that there is no significant difference between the mathematics achievement among the respondents according to socio-economic status. The findings from the study conducted by De Jesus (2023) suggest that students perceive MathScore as a valuable supplemental tool in their mathematics learning journey. The research revealed a significant difference in students' mathematics achievement based on their sex and total engagement time in MathScore per week. Moreover, academic achievement is significantly influenced by socioeconomic status, with students from higher socioeconomic backgrounds generally performing better than their counterparts from lower socioeconomic backgrounds who encounter a variety of obstacles to their academic advancement (Aashiq, Zeb, Yan, and Tahir, 2023).

Spearman's rho result on the relationship between the level of mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement at Libo-o Integrated School showed that there was a high positive correlation between mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement. The result also shows that there is a significant relationship between the level of mathematical problem-solving skills and mathematics achievement. The study conducted by Hassan and Rahman (2017) highlights the significant role of problem-solving skills and metacognitive awareness in enhancing secondary school students' mathematics achievement. It is crucial to help students develop both metacognitive awareness and problem-solving skills, as both are related to mathematics achievement.

The study aimed to address the average proficiency in mathematical problem-solving skills among seventh-grade learners by introducing an intervention titled "Mathemagical: Game-Based Activity Sheets for the Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills." The researchers created a game-based approach, incorporating three distinct activity sheets: "Math-tastic Bingo," "Math Race," and "Math and Friends Scavenger Hunt." The rationale behind the intervention was to create an effective and enjoyable learning process for students, fostering mastery in mathematical problem-solving skills. By integrating games into the educational framework, the researchers aimed to make the learning experience both engaging and meaningful. These games were specifically designed to cater to the needs of seventh-grade learners, aligning with the identified proficiency levels.

Utilizing games as a pedagogical tool in the teaching of mathematics has been recognized as an effective approach to making mathematical learning enjoyable (Beyhan and Tural, 2007; as cited by Baskahya, 2021). In the Philippines, the Department of Education created Learning Activity Sheets for all grade levels for the 2020-2021 school year. These sheets include activities like coloring, word search, mazes, and math tests. They should also use manipulative, authentic materials and accommodate cultural, linguistic, and racial diversity. Games can serve as a useful starting point for daily study (Suguitan and Natividad, 2022). Matienzo (2022), implies that providing students with supplemental worksheets that offer an appropriate level of challenge can foster motivation and active engagement in the learning process.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are presented.

1. For learners, effective mathematics learning, learners should embrace diverse activities, such as game-based sheets, to enhance problem-solving skills interactively. Collaborative learning with peers through group activities and discussions fosters a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts by incorporating different perspectives. Consistent practice using game-based activities is crucial for reinforcing comprehension and boosting confidence in mathematical problem-solving.
2. For mathematics teachers, it is recommended to enhance the learning experience by incorporating game-based activities into the curriculum. This approach not only makes the subject more engaging but also fosters a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. Recognizing the diversity in learning styles and abilities, teachers should employ differentiated instruction, combining traditional methods with game-based activities to cater to various preferences. Providing constructive feedback based on students' performance in these activities is crucial for promoting continuous learning, and helping students understand their strengths and areas for improvement.
3. For the Mathematics Department of Education Policy Makers and Learning Material Developers, it is crucial to enhance the mathematics curriculum by incorporating game-based learning strategies. This involves developing activity sheets that not only align with educational objectives but also make the learning process enjoyable for students. Additionally, emphasis should be placed on providing continuous professional development opportunities for teachers, enabling them to effectively integrate game-based learning into their teaching methods. This approach fosters a more engaging and dynamic learning environment.
4. For the community, create a nurturing learning environment at home by actively engaging in your child's education and providing access to educational games and

materials that align with classroom learning. Additionally, foster a sense of community by organizing workshops and events that center around enhancing mathematical engagement and problem-solving skills. By promoting collaboration within the community, these initiatives contribute to a supportive and enriching educational experience for all involved.

5. For parents and guardians, parents and guardians play a crucial role in fostering their child's mathematical development. Actively participating in their learning journey by discussing progress, assisting with homework, and incorporating enjoyable game-based activities can significantly enhance mathematical comprehension. Additionally, advocating for improved math education within the community and engaging with educators to understand the curriculum is essential. By supporting initiatives aimed at enhancing mathematical learning experiences, parents contribute to creating a positive and enriching environment for their children's mathematical education.

6. For future researchers, it is crucial to expand investigations into the efficacy of game-based learning in enhancing mathematics achievement and problem-solving skills. This involves exploring innovative technologies and methodologies to continually improve educational practices. Additionally, conducting longitudinal studies is recommended to comprehensively assess the enduring impact of game-based learning on students' mathematical performance and problem-solving abilities over an extended period. By delving into these areas, researchers can contribute valuable insights that can inform the ongoing development and implementation of game-based learning strategies in the realm of mathematics education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, strict adherence to ethical standards was maintained throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from the respondents prior to their participation, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose and procedures. Respondents were explicitly informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any negative repercussions. Confidentiality was strictly upheld, with all personal identifiers removed to protect the identities of the respondents. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded at all times, ensuring that their participation did not cause any harm or distress. There were no conflicts of interest influencing the conduct of the study, and the researchers ensured that all findings were presented objectively without bias. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, with all sources and references appropriately cited. The result of the study was solely for academic purposes, contributing to the improvement and mastery of mathematical problem-solving skills of the learners. Through these measures, the researchers ensured the highest standards of ethical integrity in the study.

REFERENCES

- Aashiq, K., Zeb, I., Yan, Z., Tahir, & Nazneen, A. (2023). The Impact of Socioeconomic Status on Student's Academic Achievement. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8167782>
- Amalina, I. K., & Vidákovich, T. (2023). Development and differences in mathematical problem-solving skills: A cross-sectional study of differences in demographic backgrounds. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e16366>
- Başkahya, Z. I. (2021). The effect of using game-based learning activities in algebra on seventh-grade students' algebra achievement, attitude towards mathematics and opinions about game-based learning activities [M.S. - Master of Science]. Middle East Technical University.
- Cabuquin, J. C., & Abocejo, F. T. (2023). Mathematics Learners' Performance and Academic Achievement at a Public High School Institution in Leyte, Philippines. *Formatif Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan MIPA* 13(2):123-136.
DOI:10.30998/formatif.v13i2.17235
- De Jesus, C. M. (2023). Utilization of Math Score and Mathematics Achievement of Grade 7 and 8 Students of our Lady of Peace Academy, Tuy, Batangas. Retrieved from <https://www.instabrightgazette.com/blog/utilization-of-math-score-and-mathematics-achievement-of-grade-7-and-8>
- Egorova, M. S., & Chertkova, Y. D. (2016). Sex differences in mathematical achievement: Grades, national test, and self-confidence. *Psychology in Russia*, 9(3), 4–23. <https://doi.org/10.11621/pir.2016.0301>
- Foley, B. (2018). Purposive Sampling 101. Retrieved from <https://www.alchemer.com/resources/blog/purposive-sampling-101/>
- Garinganao, N. S., & Bearneza, F. J. D. (2021). Algebraic Skills and Academic Achievement in Mathematics of Grade 7 Students in a Philippine Chinese School. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v4i3.396>
- Golla, E.F. & Reyes, A.G. (2020). PISA Mathematics Literacy Framework vis-à-vis the Kto12 Mathematics Curriculum. In M.U. Balagtas & MA. C. Montealegre (Eds), *Challenges of PISA: The PNU Report* (pp.57-100). Philippine Normal University and Rex Institute for Student Excellence, Inc.
- Guler, M. and Cekmez, E. (2023). Problem- Solving and posing skills in middle School Students. The Impact of Gender, School Type and Grade. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.202319508>
- Hassan, N. M., & Rahman, S. (2017). Problem solving skills, metacognitive awareness, and mathematics achievement: a mediation model. *New Educational Review*, 49(3), 201–212. <https://doi.org/10.15804/tner.2017.49.3.16>
- Herbert Z., Joyline C., and Elliot N. (2020). Gender Difference in Mathematics Achievement among Learners in Chipinge Secondary Schools, Zimbabwe.

Psychology and Psychological Research International Journal.

DOI:10.23880/pprij-16000244

- Incebacak, B. & Ersoy, E. (2016). Problem Solving Skills of Secondary School Students. *The China business review* 15(6):275-285. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17265/1537-1514/2016.06.002>
- Layug, G. D., Velario, J.P. V., & Capones, J. G. (2021). Teachers' Interventions in Improving Numeracy Skills of Grade 7 Students in Baguio City National High School. *Proceedings of The 4th International Conference on Advanced Research in Teaching and Education*. <https://www.doi.org/10.33422/4th.icate.2021.08.74>
- Liljedahl, P., Santos-trigo, M., Malaspina, U., & Bruder, R. (2016). Problem Solving in Mathematics Education. http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40730-2_1
- Maheswari, D. V. and Benjamin, A. E. W. (2015). Problem Solving Ability and academic achievement in Mathematics of VII Standard Students in Madurai District. *Indian Journal of Applied Research*. Volume:5, Issue 2.
- Matienzo, M. (2022). A Supplemental Worksheet in Teaching Mathematics 7. *International Journal of Research Publications*. 10.47119/IJRP1001031620223430
- Peteros, E., Gamboa, A., Etcuban, J., Dinauanao, A., Sitoy, R., & Arcadio, R. (2020). Factors affecting Mathematics Performance of Junior High School Students. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/5938>
- Prema, K. & Sathiskumar, M. (2021). Problem solving ability and academic achievement on mathematics among IX standard students. *International Research Journal and Technology*. Retrieved from <https://www.irjweb.com/Problem%20solving%20ability%20and%20academic%20achievement%20on%20mathematics%20among.pdf>
- Quinto, J. DG. (2021). Knowledge, Perceptions and Attitudes Towards Using Digital Games for Teaching and Learning. *Official Conference Proceedings. The International Academic Forum*. Retrieved from https://papers.iafor.org/wp-content/uploads/papers/ace2021/ACE2021_60947.pdf
- Raupu, S., Utari, D., Nursyamsi, & Marwiyah, S. (2022). Development of Game-Based Mathematics Students' Worksheets Integrated with Local Wisdom. *Lentera Pendidikan: Jurnal Ilmu Tarbiyah dan Keguruan*, 25(1), 172-179. <https://doi.org/10.24252/lp.2022v25n1i15>
- Rondina, J. Q. & Roble, D. (2019). Game-based Design Mathematics Activities and Students' Learning Gains. *The Turkish Online Journal of Design, Art and Communication*. Volume 9 Issue 1, p.1-7.
- Sintema, E. J., & Jita, T. (2022). Gender Differences in High School Students' Beliefs about Mathematical Problem Solving. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(10), 395–417. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.21.10.22>

- Suguitan, L. & Natividad, E. (2022). Localized Game-Based Learning Activity Sheets in Mathematics 7. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation*. 1. 210-227. 10.54536/ajmri.v1i4.723.
- TIMSS (2019). Department of Education.
<https://timssandpirls.bc.edu/timss2019/encyclopedia/pdf/Philippines.pdf>
- Vidad, D. C. & Quimbo, M.A. T. (2021). Students' Problem-solving Difficulties and Coping Strategies in Mathematics: A Model- Building Study. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, Vol. 20, No. 9, pp. 136-173.
<https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.9.9>